

The first about the last

AISDL Team

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This post is the first one in 2025. It introduces the last article written by our portal's member, Dr MH Nguyen, published on the last day of 2024 in a respected journal of the [University of Turin](#), Italy, *Visions for Sustainability*.

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How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability?

Screenshot. The last 2024 article by Dr MH Nguyen.

This published article has a quite intriguing title "[How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability?](#)" [1], connecting the two far ends of a string. One end is our shared wish for the new year 2025 and also for our healthier planet, as presented in the book co-written by this same article's author [Better Economics for the Earth](#) [2]. The other end represents a thinking journey from natural absurdity to social wisdom, through many smaller steps in the form of short satirical fables [3].

The article also features a painting by artist Bui Quang Khiem, meaningfully titled "Hot" by the artist himself. Yes, the weather is getting hot. Yes, the debate is even getting hotter. And we can also feel hot inside our head, without necessarily feeling the higher temperature. For

this reason, the painting is also used in the anthology [3].

Thus, it is our pleasure to write this first post in 2025 about the last article in 2024, with the hope for a more fruitful year of work for the better of our shared environmental concerns.

Happy New Year 2025!

References

[1] Nguyen MH. (2024). How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability?. <https://ojs.unito.it/index.php/visions/article/view/11267>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>

[3] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

